

INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT TO MEASURE THE NON-PROFIT ORGANISATION WEBSITE USER SATISFACTION AND USER WILLINGNESS TO DONATE

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ABSTRACT

A website is a popular option that has been used by non-for profit organisation (NPO) as a medium of communication. Thus, it made a website as an important medium for the NPO to communicate. The aim of this paper is an instrument validation which adopted from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The instrument validation included the website ease of use, usefulness, trust, the satisfaction of using the NPO website and the user willingness to donate. The sample size of the study was 269 website users from ten NPO website. The analysis yielded that several items were deleted to meet the CFA model fit requirement. Thus, only trusts, website ease of use, user satisfaction of using NPO website and user willingness to donate remain after the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) model fit analysis. Hence, the amended CFA model was ready to be used for the second level (measurement model) validation and reliability analysis in the Structural Equation Model (SEM).

Keywords: Website, ease of use, usefulness, trust, satisfaction, willingness to donate.

INTRODUCTION

Since 1990 were when the website introduced, it has gone through tremendous growth because of the website associated with the information and communication technology (ICT) advancement. Website use has affected various aspects of our life, especially in business strategy as a new medium to interact with the existing and potential customers. The advancement of ICT provides an opportunity for the non-profit organisation (NPO) to improve the method to solicit a donation. The website is a suitable medium to solicit donation because there are 18.6 million internet users in Malaysia (Hock Eng, Choy Yee & Devi Chuah, 2013). Also, there are 875 million customers has shopped online (Zainudin, Wan Ahmad, & Nee, 2010). Therefore, it indicated that there are massive opportunities for the NPO to communicate directly to the website users. It seemed that the website could generate opportunities for the non-profit sector as similar to the for-profit sector.

From the time the website was introduced, the website has shown many significant roles to meet its function as the new business model for the NPO. Website helps to shape and maintain the NPO identity and reputation (Madichie & Hinson, 2013; Sriramesh, Rivera-Sanchez, & Soriano, 2012), promoting fundraising activities and increase awareness (Diaz, Blasquez & Molina, & Martin-Consuegra, 2013; Shier & Handy, 2012; Reddick & Ponomariov, 2012), offering relevant information (Uzunoglu & Misci Kip, 2013; Sommerfeldt, Kent, and Taylor, 2012; Zainudin,

Ahmad, & Nee, 2010), to response to user enquiries (Sharma & Lijuan, 2015), to educate by establishing interaction with multiple publics (Sharma & Lijuan, 2015; Ingenhoof, Koelling, 2010; Kang & Norton, 2004) and to generate income (Zainudin, Ahmad, and Nee, 2010).

Although there are many opportunities and factors indicated website significant functions to encourage the non-profit sector to use the website as an alternative medium to solicit a donation and to interact with the website users, yet, many NPO failed to utilise their website optimally. The NPO website failed to serve the NPO particular purpose (McMahon, Seaman & Lemley, 2015). NPO website often lacks required information that is important to attract user attention (Wong and Jusoff, 2011). Also, the website was poorly designed (Abdullah, Husin, Hasan, Husain, & Yahya, 2010). Thus, this study wishes to highlight an important question whether the suggested website quality is met the study scale development and validity. This study believed it is important to create guidelines for the non-profit sector to enhance the NPO website function via relevant website concept such as adopted from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

There are many website constructs and information system (IS) which may influence website user action such as to donate. Thus, the study aware that to test every available construct and possible IS that suitable for the non-profit sector are time-consuming at a high cost. However, it still important to ensure the instrument is reliable and valid to develop the guidelines. Thus, the study decided to apply the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to help this research overcome the reliability and validity issue conveniently. Besides that, the study also using the validated items from previous research yet in a different context. Therefore, this paper objective is to confirm the validity and reliability of the proposed constructs that is the website usefulness, ease of use, trust, the satisfaction of using the NPO website, and user willingness to donate are met user preferences.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This research adopted the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to understand the user decision-making process and the user willingness to donate. According to TAM, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, satisfaction, and intention have been theorized to influence user decision making process and usage (Agag & El-Masry, 2016; Akman & Mishra, 2015; Green & Pearson, 2011). For example, Escobar-Rodríguez, and Bonsón-Fernández (2017) integrating a set of variables and TAM to analyse the factors that determine users intention to purchase fashion online. Agrebi and Jallais (2015) proposed an extended TAM to improve an understanding of user intention to purchase using a smartphone. Zhu, Lin, and Hsu (2012) adopted TAM to investigate the factors to influence online games acceptance. While, Wu, Chou, Weng, and Huang (2011) assimilate TAM as a research framework to explore the relationship of web 2.0 features with user's action. TAM is suitable to understand users' perception in e-service for online shopping (Lee & Wu, 2011). Whereas, Islam (2009) use TAM to understand consumer behaviour on the interactive retail website. TAM is a reasonable predictor of users' intention to use information technology (Li, 2009). TAM also widely accepted information system (IS) model that suitable to understand and to predict users' acceptance of information system (Tseng, Hsu, & Chuang, 2012). Therefore, the research reckoned it is possible to assimilate TAM to understand the user decision-making process and action. The research suggested to include trust and satisfaction of using the NPO website in the existing TAM together with the existing TAM elements that are perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and user willingness to donate because trust and satisfaction are the main causal factors in e-commerce success (Kim, Ferrin, & Rhao, 2009).

Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

PU refers to the level to which the user believes the new technology would enhance the job performance while PEOU is referring to the user's belief that using the technology would take

minimal effort (Davis, 1989). Besides, PU also denotes as the degree which consumers believe technology would facilitate transaction process and PEOU means to the degree to which consumers believe that using technology will be free from the effort (Green & Pearson, 2011). Also, PU reflects user perceived utility when browsing the e-commerce website, and PEOU showed user perceived difficulty when using e-commerce website (Zhou & Zhang, 2009). Leng, Lada, Muhammad, Ibrahim and Amboala (2011) findings indicate user would perceive a website as useful if it is easy to use. Thus, this research thinks a website should provide positive surfing experience to avoid user to change to another website

Trust

Rusman, Van Bruggen and Koper (2007) indicated perceived trust is the belief of individual in something that is believable and desirable to trust whereas Kate (2009) stated trust is an attitude and works only between the trustor and recipient. Trust is a relationship between the trustor and trustee to fulfil the mutual benefit (Gregg & Walczak, 2010). Trust refers to the belief, expectation, word and the promise by the online service provider that is reliable where the seller shall not use this advantage to harm the users (Green & Pearson, 2011).

Trust would determine the success of an e-commerce website (Elbeltagi & Agag, 2016; Shin, Chung, Oh & Lee, 2013). Trust will provide an encouraging condition to ensure the success of the transaction (Lee and Wu, 2011). Trust is an important element in e-commerce business (Gregg & Walczak, 2010). Trust also imperative features to be included in developing a website (Chen, Hsu, & Lin, 2010). Zhou and Zhang (2009) findings show that trust also significant to PU. Thus, trust is an important feature of a website because it may reduce user perceive risk. A website which has a little risk probably more useful to the website user. Additionally, trust also significant to influence website user intention, for example for online hotel booking (Wang, Guillet, Hung, & Fong, 2015). Despite the importance of trust, the study noticed its lack in the NPO website context and it is relevant to analyse user preference on trust.

Satisfaction of Using The Npo Website

Satisfaction refers to the user level of satisfy to the product and service provided (Nawi, Al Mamun & Raston, 2015). While satisfaction in the website context means user feeling, attitude and expectation of good service to visit and repurchase (Sharma & Lijuan, 2015). Whereas according to Green and Pearson (2011), satisfaction refers to user post evaluation experience such as positive, negative or neutral. The user is satisfied when they perceive overall system features as pleasant and easy to use (Sharma & Baoku, 2013). The success of information technology is related to user perceive of PU and PEOU (Ho, Kuo, & Lin, 2012). PU and PEOU are significant to determine consumer attitude and satisfaction (Green & Pearson, 2011).

Trust show significant relationship affecting user satisfaction (Sharma & Lijuan, 2015). There is a positive effect of trust and satisfaction relationship in Brazil finance service (Ferreira, de Freitas, Nunes & Giovanni (2014). Trust is directly related to satisfaction because trust is an important factor to reduce negative user perception of the online transaction such as anonymity and risk (Sharma & Baoku, 2013). Shin, Chung, Oh, and Lee (2013) findings indicate trust shows a significant relationship with satisfaction. Trust is an imperative factor to ensure user satisfaction for the online game website (Sharma & Baoku, 2012). The success of business-consumer relationship in e-commerce is related to the presence of trust and satisfaction because trust is an important element in creating user confidence (Kim, Ferrin & Rhao, 2009). Trust is the largest effect affecting user satisfaction (Zhou & Zhang, 2009).

User Willingness to Donate

This research is adopting willingness definition by De Massis, Kotlar, Chua, and Chrisman (2014) that is a favourable quality to engage in distinct behaviour included an intention and motivation. While Delone and McLean (2013) denoted, the intention refers an attitude such as

intention to use. Therefore, user willingness is parallel to the user intention and can be used as a user action. Many previous studies supported the significant relation between user satisfaction and intention such as intention to use the website (Belanche, Casalo', & Guinali'u, 2012), purchase intention (Lau, Kwek, & Tan, 2010; Hsu, Chang, & Chen, 2011; Bai, Law, & Wen, 2008) and repurchase intention (Zhou, Lu & Wang, 2009). Besides that, Nawi, Al Mamun and Raston (2015) finding indicated a significant relationship between user satisfaction and user action. Also, 90 percent of the satisfied customer will share their satisfaction with others, and 80 percent of them will repurchase (Meyer, 2008; Zainuddin, Ahmad, & Nee, 2010).

METHOD

Development of Instrument for Survey

The main unit for observation of this research is the respondents who had an experience at least once browsing the selected NPO website which is listed under the Putra Brand Award 2010. The study distributed 400 online surveys to the NPO volunteers that listed in the NPO database because the NPO volunteers are the active NPO website users. The respondents were given two weeks to complete the survey. Thus, after two weeks, the process had successfully collected 269 valid responses.

Kline (2015) suggested that to perform Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), a large sample is required (more than 200 samples). Hence the research believed 269 valid responses are adequate to perform SEM as a statistical analysis.

The user satisfaction of using the NPO website can be measured via three constructs namely the perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and trust. The items are adopted from the previous study to measure each construct. The perceived usefulness consists of 4 items (refer table 1), perceived ease of use consists of 4 items (refer table 2), and trust consists of 5 items (refer table 3). While 11 items can measure user satisfaction of using the NPO website (refer table 4) and nine items can measure the impact of user satisfaction to user willingness to donate (refer table 5).

Formerly the instrument content validity was refined by three experts from Faculty of Modern Languages and Communication at University Putra Malaysia. Every item was measured using five Point Likert scale with 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (slightly agree), 4 (agree), 5 (strongly agree) except for user satisfaction of using NPO website was rated using 1 (not at all satisfied), 2 (Slightly satisfied), 3 (Moderately satisfied), 4 (Very satisfied, and 5 (Extremely satisfied).

Table 1: Constructs and Items for Perceived Usefulness

CONSTRUCT	QUESTIONS	ADOPTED FROM
PU	The website is well organised (PU1). The website provided me with complete information on the current issue (PU2). The website provided me with the latest information on the current issue (PU3). The website provided me with accurate information on the current issue (PU4).	Xu, Benbasat, and Centefelli (2013) Green and Pearson (2011) Zhou and Zhang (2009)

Table 2: Constructs and Items for Perceived ease of use

CONSTRUCT	QUESTIONS	ADOPTED FROM
PEOU	It was easy to ask the website to do what I want (PEOU1). It was easy to search for the current issue on the website (PEOU2). It was easy to access the website system to get the current issue (PEOU3). It only took a while to download the current issue (PEOU4).	Xu, Benbasat, and Centefelli (2013) Green and Pearson (2011) Zhou and Zhang (2009)

Table 3: Constructs and items for Trust

CONSTRUCT	QUESTIONS	ADOPTED FROM
TRU	I could access the website from the latest technology device (TRU1). The website is dependable (TRU2). The website provided a prompt response to my inquiries (TRU3). The website bears my interest in mind (TRU4). I felt confident with the website (TRU5).	Chen, Rungruengsamrit, and Chen (2013) Green and Pearson (2011) Zhou and Zhang (2009)

Table 4: Constructs and items for the satisfaction of using NPO website

CONSTRUCT	QUESTIONS	ADOPTED FROM
SAT	The current information provided by the website (SAT1). The system to search for the current issue (SAT2). The website service to search for the current issue (SAT3). The website easiness (SAT4). The website usefulness (SAT5). The website trustworthiness (SAT6). The website reliability (SAT7). The website empathies (SAT8). The website responsiveness (SAT9). The website assurance (SAT10). The website tangible (SAT11).	Chen, Rungruengsamrit, and Chen (2013) Xu, Benbasat, and Centefelli (2013) Zhou and Zhang (2009)

Table 5: Constructs and items for user willingness to donate

DIMENSION	QUESTIONS	ADOPTED FROM
WIL	I am willing to use the NPO website to know the current issue (WIL1). I am willing to use the NPO website to donate (WIL2). I am willing to donate RM 1 (WIL3). I am willing to donate RM 5 (WIL4). I am willing to donate RM 10 (WIL5). I am willing to donate more than RM 10 (WIL6). I am willing to donate to NPO in the social sector (WIL7). I am willing to donate to NPO in the health sector (WIL8). I am willing to donate to NPO in the environmental sector (WIL9).	Chen, Rungruengsamrit, and Chen (2013) Xu, Benbasat, and Centefelli (2013)

DATA COLLECTION

Before the actual data collection, thirty website user from Malaysian Red Crescent tested the instrument. The finding indicated that the Cronbach's Alpha value for the instrument composite reliability is from 0.816 to 0.946 (refer to table 6). According to Nunally and Bernstein (1994), Cronbach's Alpha value more than 0.70 indicated the instrument is satisfactorily meet the reliability requirement.

Table 6: Composite Reliability of the Research Instrument

VARIABLES	NO. OF ITEMS	CRONBACH ALPHA
		Pre-Test (n=30)
Satisfaction	11	0.946
Perceived Usefulness	4	0.937
Willingness to donate	9	0.891
Perceived Ease of Use	4	0.847
Trust	5	0.816

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

For the actual data collection, the research collected 269 valid responses. Each construct was validated using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for its validity and reliability using the Analysis Moment of Structure (AMOS). According to Hair, Black, Babin, and Anderson (2009) that CFA is a reliable technique to assist researchers in defining the essential structure of variables. CFA indicated the items for each construct are interrelated and represent the variable. CFA included model fit, convergent validity and construct reliability analysis. Thus, any item or construct will be discarded if it failed to meet the model fitness, validity and reliability criteria because the discarded item did not belong and represent the variable.

CFA for Perceived Usefulness (PU)

No items deleted for PU due to it met the recommended rules as suggested by Bryne and Hair, et al. (2010). The items showed factor loading value more 0.5 but less than 1.0 (Refer table 7). The factor loading assessment showed the items in PU were not weak and low error.

Table 7: Factor Loading value for PU

ITEMS	FACTOR LOADING	AVE	CR
PU 1	.754	NA	NA
PU 2	.857		
PU 3	.833		
PU 4	.717		

Also, the PU validity and reliability as a construct determined via model fit. The finding indicated PU failed to show good model fit as recommended by Hair et al. (2010). The RMSEA value was 0.17, and exceeded the recommended value for absolute fit category, while the relative chi-square value (χ^2/df) is 8.763 and surpassed the recommended value for the parsimonious fit category (refer table 8). Due to the reason PU failed to pass the model fit test, PU is not eligible for convergence validity (AVE) and construct reliability (CR) test. Therefore, the CFA indicated PU failed to meet scale development and validity.

PU also will be discarded for the second level (measurement model) construct validation due to it failed to meet the CFA requirement in SEM analysis.

Table 8: Table fitness PU

NAME OF CATEGORY	MODEL FIT INDICES	RECOMMENDED VALUE	FIT INDICES VALUE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	<= .08	.17
	GFI	>=.9	.96
Parsimonious Fit	X²/df	< 5.0	8.763
Incremental Fit	AGFI	>=.9	.83
	CFI	>=.9	.97
	NFI	>=.9	.96
	TLI	>=.9	.91

CFA for Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

For the PEOU, no item also was deleted due to the items met the recommended rules to determine model fit. The items showed factor loading value from 0.65 to 0.85 (refer table 9). Also, the model fit for PEOU also met the suggested criteria (refer table 10).

Table 9: Factor loading value for PEOU

ITEMS	FACTOR LOADING	AVE	CR
PEOU 1	.753	.580	.846
PEOU 2	.855		
PEOU 3	.770		
PEOU 4	.655		

Table 10: Table fitness PEOU

NAME OF CATEGORY	MODEL FIT INDICES	RECOMMENDED VALUE	FIT INDICES VALUE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	<= .08	.05
	GFI	>=.9	.99
Parsimonious Fit	X ² /df	< 5.0	1.895
Incremental Fit	AGFI	>=.9	.96
	CFI	>=.9	.99
	NFI	>=.9	.99
	TLI	>=.9	.98

Additionally, the validity of the item was also measured via convergent validity analysis to determine the items were properly converged to measure one construct. Hair et al. (2009) suggested Average Variance Extracted (AVE) can be used to measure the convergent validity and the value must be more than 0.5. Table 9 indicated the AVE value is 0.580. Thus it met the convergent validity requirement. Besides, construct reliability analysis is used to measure the reliability of the items. Table 9 showed PEOU construct reliability is 0.846 and met the construct reliability requirement as suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) that value for construct reliability must be more than 0.7. Thus, PEOU is met the scale development and validity, and ready for the second level (measurement model) construct validation in SEM analysis.

CFA for Trust

The analysis showed one item in trust were deleted to obtain the model fitness. Table 11 indicated the factor loading for the items is between 0.62 to 0.74. While table 12 showed the Trust is met the model fit requirement.

Table 11: Factor Loading value for Trust

ITEMS	FACTOR LOADING	AVE	CR
Tru 1	.734	.549	.828
Tru 2	.842		
Tru 3	.629		
Tru 5	.743		

Table 12: Table fitness Trust

NAME OF CATEGORY	MODEL FIT INDICES	RECOMMENDED VALUE	FIT INDICES VALUE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	<= .08	.04
	GFI	>=.9	.99
Parsimonious Fit	X ² /df	< 5.0	1.603
Incremental Fit	AGFI	>=.9	.96
	CFI	>=.9	.99
	NFI	>=.9	.99
	TLI	>=.9	.99

Also, convergent validity analysis indicated trust met the criteria. Table 11 showed the AVE value is 0.549. While the construct reliability is 0.828, also met the construct reliability requirement. Hence, trust is met the scale development and validity, and ready for the second level (measurement model) of construct validity and reliability in SEM.

CFA for Satisfaction of Using the NPO Website

One item during CFA Satisfaction analysis due to lower factor loading. The remaining items showed factor loading value between 0.66 to 0.74 (refer to table 13). While table 14 showed the satisfaction of using the NPO website met the model fit requirement.

Table 13: Factor loading value for the satisfaction of using the NPO website

ITEMS	FACTOR LOADING	AVE	CR
Sat 1	.712	.501	.909
Sat 2	.702		
Sat 3	.693		
Sat 4	.712		
Sat 5	.707		
Sat 6	.717		
Sat 7	.728		
Sat 8	.747		
Sat 9	.660		
Sat 10	.697		

Table 14: Table fitness for the satisfaction of using the NPO website

NAME OF CATEGORY	MODEL FIT INDICES	RECOMMENDED VALUE	FIT INDICES VALUE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	$\leq .08$.08
	GFI	$\geq .9$.93
Parsimonious Fit	X ² /df	< 5.0	3.028
Incremental Fit	AGFI	$\geq .9$.89
	CFI	$\geq .9$.94
	NFI	$\geq .9$.92
	TLI	$\geq .9$.92

Further analysis of convergent validity showed that satisfaction of using the NPO website is 0.501 and met the criteria. While the construct reliability is 0.909 also met the reliability criteria. Therefore, the satisfaction of using the NPO website is met the scale development and validity, and ready for the second level (measurement model) analysis using SEM.

CFA FOR USER WILLINGNESS TO DONATE

The analysis on user willingness to donate revealed that two items were deleted due to low factor loading value, while the remaining items showed a value between 0.66 to 0.83 (refer table 15) and met the factor loading requirement. The construct also met the model fit requirement as illustrated in table 16.

Table 15: Factor loading value for user willingness to donates

ITEMS	FACTOR LOADING	AVE	CR
Wil 1	.667	.573	.903
Wil 4	.700		
Wil 5	.743		
Wil 6	.807		
Wil 7	.830		
Wil 8	.757		
Wil 9	.783		

Table 16: Table fitness for user willingness to donate

NAME OF CATEGORY	MODEL FIT INDICES	RECOMMENDED VALUE	FIT INDICES VALUE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	<= .08	.07
	GFI	>=.9	.96
Parsimonious Fit	X²/df	< 5.0	2.624
Incremental Fit	AGFI	>=.9	.92
	CFI	>=.9	.97
	NFI	>=.9	.96
	TLI	>=.9	.96

Additional analysis, for convergent validity, indicated the items for user willingness to donate is properly converge. The AVE value is 0.573 (refer to table 15). While the construct reliability for user willingness to donate is 0.903 and met the reliability standards (refer to table 15). The finding for an individual analysis of website quality elements indicated that the NPO website user preferred to all suggested elements except the PU. In addition, the preferred construct is met the scale development and validity, and ready for the second level (measurement model) analysis using SEM.

CONCLUSION

Validation of the instrument is a must before measuring the website ease of use, usefulness, and trust towards the website user satisfaction of using the NPO website and influence the user action. Therefore, this paper is to validate the proposed items for website easiness, usefulness, and trust through the CFA. The variables of website ease of use, usefulness, the satisfaction of using NPO website and user willingness to donate adopted from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). While Trust included due to it is significant to the application of many IS medium such as the website. The result from CFA indicated several items were discarded to meet the model fit criteria. Consequently, website usefulness discarded, one item deleted for website trust, one item also was deleted for user satisfaction of using NPO website, and out of nine items, seven items remained for the user willingness to donate. Whereas, the convergence validity analysis for the items of website ease of use, trust, the satisfaction of using NPO website and user willingness to donate indicated the items are independent but converged to measure as an individual construct. Additionally, further analysis of construct reliability showed website ease of use, trust, the satisfaction of using the NPO website and the user willingness to donate are reliable. The items in this study met scale development, valid and reliable and ready for the second level of validity and reliability analysis in SEM. The CFA is a crucial process to identify relevant variables that suitable to use in analysing the relationship between the variables.

The finding will enable further analysis to determine the website user willingness to donate when the user is browsing the NPO website based on the proposed variables. From the theoretical perspective, this study adds new knowledge to the NPO website study in Malaysia especially the suitable variables to use for the NPO website development. The research examines the antecedents of website quality from the NPO website user perspective through robust IS model and validated the theory in the NPO website quality context. The study confirms the remaining item in PEOU, trust, the satisfaction of using the NPO website, and user willingness to donate are met the scale development and validity. Also, the finding of this research has relevant practical implications for the NPO to develop or to revamp a website that able to meet user satisfaction. The knowledge of the antecedents of website quality is useful for the NPO to develop a better website which aligns to their strategies and activities aimed to increase donation. In addition, trust and PEOU play a critical role to meet the NPO website user preference.

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